

**Standard Potential of the Cell $\text{Hg} \mid \text{Hg}_2\text{Cl}_2, \text{HCl} \mid \text{HCl} \mid \text{HCl} \text{ Q. H.} \mid \text{Pt}$ &
 (c) | (c) (c) |
 Activity Coefficient of Hydrochloric Acid at 5°, 15°, 25° and 35°**

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The standard potential of the cell $\text{Hg} \mid \text{Hg}_2\text{Cl}_2, \text{HCl} \mid \text{HCl} \mid \text{HCl} \text{ Q. H.} \mid \text{Pt}$, where Q.H. stands for quinhydrone, has been determined at 5°, 15°, 25° and 35°C. The values are 0.44145, 0.43620, 0.43145 and 0.42745 volt respectively. The activity coefficient of hydrochloric acid at various concentrations has also been calculated at these temperatures.

Cells of the type $\text{Hg} \mid \text{Hg}_2\text{Cl}_2, \text{HCl} (c_1) \mid \text{HCl} (c_1) \mid \text{HCl} (c'_1) \text{ Q. H.} \mid \text{Pt}$ and
 $\text{MCl}_2(c_2) \mid \text{MCl}_2(c_2) \mid \text{MCl}_2(c_2)$

$\text{Hg} \mid \text{Hg}_2\text{Cl}_2, \text{HCl} (c_1) \mid \text{HCl} (c_1) \mid \text{HCl} (c_1) \mid \text{Q. H.} \mid \text{Pt}$ have been used by
 $\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4(c_2) \mid \text{H}_2\text{SO}_4(c_2) \mid \text{H}_2\text{SO}_4(c_2)$

us for determining the dissociation constants of MCl^+ , MCl_2 and HSO_4^- at 5°, 15° 25° and 35°C. These determinations require a knowledge of the standard potential of the cell $\text{Hg} \mid \text{Hg}_2\text{Cl}_2, \text{HCl} \mid \text{HCl} \mid \text{HCl} \text{ Q. H.} \mid \text{Pt}$ which has been measured at these temperatures and forms the basis of this paper.

EXPERIMENTAL

The electrode and bridge vessels were similar to those used by Prasad and co-workers¹. Pure and redistilled mercury was used in the preparation of the calomel half cells. Mercurous chloride and the calomel half cell were prepared as recommended by Hills and Ives² except that the silicone treatment was not done. Analytical grade (Renal, Budapest) quinhydrone was recrystallised and dried following the method of Harned and Wright³. Hydrochloric acid (A. R. quality) was standardised by borax and the strength was confirmed gravimetrically by silver chloride method. All solutions were made with double distilled water at the temperature at which they were used. Pure nitrogen, saturated with water vapour by passing the gas through the experimental solution, was used to remove air from both the calomel and the quinhydrone half cells. The temperature of the air thermostats was constant within $\pm 0.05^\circ$. All contacts with the cell were made through mercury with the help of platinum wires. The measurements were made with a Bajaj Vernier Potentiometer which agreed with the measurements made with Tinsley Vernier Potentiometer.

1. S. Nath, S. Aditya and B. Prasad, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1951, **28**, 683.
2. G. J. Hills and D. J. G. Ives, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, p. 311.
3. H. S. Harned and D. D. Wright, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, **55**, 4849.

Four readings consisting of duplicate experiments performed by each L. Sharma and G. Sahu agreed within ± 0.1 mv at 5°, 15° and 25° and within ± 0.15 mv at 35°. All the concentrations are expressed in gram moles per litre. The e.m.f. values given in table I are the mean of the four readings taken.

TABLE I

[HCl]	Observed e.m.f. in volt			
	5°	15°	25°	35°
0.005	0.18385	0.16940	0.15526	0.14193
0.010	0.21592	0.20256	0.18956	0.17748
0.020	0.24770	0.23542	0.22355	0.21255
0.035	0.27312	0.26149	0.25065	0.24040
0.050	0.2917	0.27822	0.26794	0.25803
0.075	0.30762	0.29740	0.28753	0.27819
0.100	0.32023	0.31062	0.30163	0.29254

DISCUSSION

The e.m.f. of the cell Hg | Hg₂Cl₂·HCl | HCl | HCl Q.H. | Pt is given by

$$E = E_0 + \frac{RT}{F} \ln [H^+] \times [Cl^-] + 2.3026 \frac{RT}{F} \log f^+ f^- \dots \dots (1)$$

The activity coefficient product can be expressed by

$$-\log f^+ f^- = \frac{2A\sqrt{\mu}}{1 + \sqrt{\mu}} - B_1\mu \dots \dots (2)$$

as well as by ; $-\log f^+ f^- = 2A\sqrt{\mu} - B_2\mu \dots \dots (3)$

Combining equations (1) and (2), we get

$$E - \frac{RT}{F} \ln [H^+] \times [Cl^-] + 2.3026 \frac{RT}{F} \frac{2A\sqrt{\mu}}{1 + \sqrt{\mu}} = E_0 + 2.3026 \frac{RT}{F} B_1\mu \dots \dots (4)$$

Similarly by combining equations (1) and (3) we get

$$E - \frac{RT}{F} \ln [H^+] \times [Cl^-] + 2.3026 \frac{RT}{F} 2A\sqrt{\mu} = E_0 + 2.3026 \frac{RT}{F} B_2\mu \dots \dots (5)$$

The values⁴ of A are taken as 0.4921, 0.5002, 0.5092 and 0.5190 at 5°, 15°, 25° and 35° respectively. By plotting separately the left hand side of equations (4) and (5) against μ , straight lines were obtained, the intercepts of which gave the same values for E_0 . The slopes of the lines gave the values of B_1 and B_2 . It may be noted that almost all the points fell on the lines and the lines were drawn in such a manner that when the adjacent points were joined, equal areas were covered both above and below the line concerned. Using the values of B_1 and B_2 , $f^+ f^-$ which is equal to $f^2 \pm$ was

4. G. G. Manov, R. G. Bates, W. J. Hamer and S. F. Acree, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1943, 65, 1765.

calculated with the help of equations (2) and (3). There is no significant difference in the values of f_{\pm} obtained from equations (2) and (3). The results are tabulated below. Algebraic sum of the E_0 values of the calomel⁵ and the quinhydrone⁶ electrodes are given inside the bracket.

T A B L E II

Standard Potential of the Cell.

Temp. °C	5	15	25	35
E_0	0.44145 (0.44148)	0.43620 (0.43626)	0.43145 (0.43160)	0.42745 (0.42748)

T A B L E III

Activity Coefficients of Hydrochloric Acid

(Our values are outside and Harned and Ehlers⁷ values* where available are inside the brackets).

[HCl]	5°C	15°C	25°C	35°C
0.005	0.9303 (0.9302)	0.9293 (0.9295)	0.9280 (0.9285)	0.9266 (0.9272)
0.010	0.9067 (0.9056)	0.9054 (0.9051)	0.9038 (0.9043)	0.9019 (0.9025)
0.020	0.8780 (0.8774)	0.8764 (0.8767)	0.8743 (0.8755)	0.8717 (0.8728)
0.035	0.8516 0.8340	0.8498 0.8323	0.8474 0.8295	0.8441 0.8258
0.050	(0.8342)	(0.8327)	(0.8304)	(0.8265)
0.075	0.8145	0.8127	0.8097	0.8054
0.100	0.8016 (0.8022)	0.8001 (0.7999)	0.7951 (0.7964)	0.7920 (0.7915)

* Molarity and molality do not differ appreciably upto 0.100 M.

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6. R. G. Bates, "Electrometric pH Determinations", p. 175, Wiley, New York, 1954.
7. H. S. Harned and R. W. Ehlers, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, **55**, 2179.